

STRATEGIZING OPEN INNOVATION: KEY APPROACHES FOR MODERN ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper investigates and evaluates various open innovation strategies that contemporary businesses can use to strengthen their competitive position. It examines key approaches such as co-creation, crowdsourcing, intellectual property sharing, hackathons, and open-source development.

Methodology/approach – The methodology combines a comprehensive literature review with case studies of leading companies that have successfully implemented these strategies. This approach provides insights into the practical application and benefits of open innovation strategies.

Findings – The findings reveal that open innovation enables firms to leverage external ideas and technologies, resulting in accelerated innovation, reduced costs, and increased adaptability in dynamic markets. The research highlights the importance of integrating these strategies to build a robust innovation ecosystem.

Research limitations/implications – The study is limited by its reliance on secondary data and case studies, which may not capture the full spectrum of open innovation practices across different industries. Future research should involve empirical studies to validate these findings and explore the challenges enterprises face in implementing open innovation.

Practical implications – Businesses should adopt a strategic approach to open innovation, fostering collaboration both within and outside the organization to drive continuous improvement and growth.

Originality/value – This paper demonstrates that open innovation strategies are interconnected and can create a synergetic effect that amplifies their individual benefits.

Key words: *open innovation, co-creation, crowdsourcing.*

Introduction

In recent years, open innovation has gained increasing popularity as enterprises seek to gain a competitive edge, constantly revolutionizing the way companies approach research and development. Unlike closed innovation, which relies solely on internal resources and ideas, open innovation embraces external contributions, facilitating a more dynamic and diverse approach to problem-solving.

Open innovation is variously described as a process, as a set of relationships between companies or as a cognitive paradigm. This paradigm gained popularity with the release of Henry Chesbrough's book "Open Innovation: The New Imperative" in 2003, where Chesbrough stated that companies "can and should use both internal and external ideas, and paths to market, as they look to advance their technology" (Chesbrough, 2003). Therefore, open innovation involves organizations working together and collaborating, sharing ideas, experiences, and technologies to generate value that could not be achieved if the work would be conducted in isolation.

An important aspect is that strategies such as crowdsourcing, hackathons, and co-creation are at the forefront of this paradigm shift, enabling companies to accelerate innovation, reduce costs, and enhance their adaptability in rapidly changing markets. Thus, the research conducted based on extensive literature review, aims to define practical implications of the open innovation strategies adopted in time. The main objective is to present the existing open innovation strategies and to highlight how those strategies are implemented within organizational setting.

Open innovation strategies

Co-creation

Open innovation emphasizes active collaboration between various organizations and the sharing of intellectual property, while co-creation specifically focuses on the relationship between an organization and a defined group of stakeholders, most commonly customers. One of the most well-known definitions of this concept describes co-creation as "an active, creative, and social process based on collaboration between producers and users, initiated by the firm to generate value for customers" (Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2000). This definition highlights the fact that co-creation involves more than just collaboration with end-users, requiring an exchange of knowledge and resources to deliver personalized experiences.

Co-creation is included in the open innovation strategies as it involves consumers directly in organizational processes, therefore generating value. Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2000) point out that co-creation is used to define a new category of consumers, the "active" consumers, who are directly involved in the processes of the organization. This involvement transforms the traditional passive consumer role into an active one, where customers participate in the process of value creation.

Based on this foundation, Gronroos (2012) makes a step further and defines co-creation as "a collaborative activity involving all parties in direct interactions, aiming to contribute to the value generated for one or both parties." This perspective underscores the mutual benefits derived from co-creation, where both the organization and the customers gain value through direct interaction and collaboration. In practice, co-creation can take various forms, including customer feedback sessions, co-design workshops, and online platforms where customers can contribute with different ideas and innovations. By involving customers in the innovation process, firms can leverage the collective intelligence and creativity of their user base, leading to more innovative and personalized products and services. This active participation fosters a deeper connection with customers, enhances customer satisfaction, and ultimately drives business success. Thus, we can say that co-creation, as an integral part of open innovation, represents a powerful strategy for companies aiming to stay competitive in today's rapidly evolving market landscape.

Crowdsourcing

Crowdsourcing harnesses the collective intelligence of a large group of people, typically through online platforms, to generate innovative ideas and solutions. Jeff Howe coined the term in 2006, describing it as a method where organizations use the internet to outsource tasks traditionally performed by employees, to a large, undefined group of people via open calls (Howe, 2006).

In the same manner, Prpic (2015) asserts that crowdsourcing can be viewed as the utilization of the IT industry to outsource business responsibilities, leveraging the collective power of a crowd to achieve previously unattainable goals and gain an advantage. The focus of crowdsourcing is on these groups of people, known as crowds, which consist of individuals from various locations around the world, most commonly connected through online platforms. The tasks addressed to the crowd, can vary in complexity, and the crowd is expected to contribute through "work, funding, knowledge, or experiences" ensuring mutual benefits: the users gain "economic, social, or individual skill development satisfaction", while organizations leverage these contributions to gain competitive advantages (Arolas and Guevara, 2012).

According to Brabham (2013), the control of the process of creating goods and ideas in crowdsourcing should be positioned to maximize "the benefits of a traditional top-down approach with those of an open and creative bottom-up approach". When this activity is too strictly controlled by the organization, such as in a simple preference contest, the crowd becomes merely a pawn in the organization's broader objectives, with the benefits oriented more towards the organization for publicity reasons. On the other hand, when control is more community-driven, as seen within platforms like Wikipedia or other open-source projects, the crowd self-governs and sets its own strategic goals, with the organization playing a less significant role, generally serving as a hosting platform.

LEGO Ideas is a prime example of crowdsourcing, where the company leverages the creativity and innovation of its fan community to generate new product ideas. Through the LEGO Ideas platform, fans can submit their own designs for new LEGO sets. These submissions are then open to votes from other community members. If a design receives enough support, typically 10,000 votes, it is reviewed by a group of LEGO employees for potential production as an official LEGO set. This approach allows LEGO to tap into a diverse pool of talent and creativity, benefiting from the collective intelligence of their community. The crowd benefits by seeing their designs potentially turned into real products, often with public recognition and monetary rewards, while LEGO gains fresh, market-validated product ideas that help them in maintaining and growing their product line. This model is just one of the many more, exemplifying how crowdsourcing can create a symbiotic relationship between a company and its customers, leading to innovative and popular products.

Intellectual Property Sharing and Licensing

Given that innovation is increasingly driven by user contributions and collective effort, we can argue that companies must recalibrate their intellectual property rights management strategies to successfully adapt to this shift. It is essential for them to develop methodologies that strike a delicate balance between traditional and isolated approaches necessary for the legal acquisition of intellectual property rights and the integration of transparency to transition towards an open innovation process (Lee et al., 2010).

Chesbrough (2003) suggests that in the age of open innovation, companies should encourage and facilitate a diverse approach to intellectual property, allowing ideas and technologies to flow more freely between different organizations and sectors. Unlike closed innovation, which promotes strict control and exclusivity over internally developed intellectual property,

Chesbrough (2003) views intellectual property as an asset that can be licensed or shared to accelerate innovation and achieve mutually beneficial advantages.

Bogers, Bekkers, and Granstrand (2012) argue that protecting the intellectual property and controlling the use of inventions are key aspects of many firms' strategies, but in order to succeed in open innovation, firms must share knowledge with others. Licensing can take various forms, including exclusive licensing, grant-back licensing, which allows the licensor to use the improvements made by the licensee to the licensed technology, or patent pools, where multiple patent holders license their technologies to each other to facilitate the development of new products (Bogers, Bekkers, and Granstrand, 2012). These licensing strategies must align with the strategic objectives of open innovation and contribute to the creation of new business models and collaborative approaches within innovation ecosystems.

Hackathons

Hackathons are intensive collaboration and programming events, regarded as a tool or strategy of open innovation, bringing together participants from diverse fields to develop innovative and sustainable solutions to complex social and industrial challenges within a short timeframe. These events are designed to foster creativity, rapid prototyping, and collaborative problem-solving. The term "hackathon" combines "marathon" and "hacking," originating in the 1960s when students would gather for intense programming sessions resembling a marathon, often lasting 24 hours.

Mehta and Shah (2022) describe hackathons as an open innovation strategy that reveals competencies and skills in a manner that encourages collaborative innovation and the emergence of creative solutions. In the same spirit, Franco, Presenza and Petruzzelli (2022) categorize hackathons as strategies that generate innovative ideas, emphasizing their ability to bring together diverse actors and generate value through intensive collaboration and focused brainstorming.

A thorough definition of the hackathon is offered by Halvari et al. (2020), who characterize it as "one type of organized, goal-driven innovation contest, a short timebounded event with a challenge to be solved creatively in cooperation and collocation of teams, whose results are presented and recognized in a ceremony at the end of the event". This definition highlights the essential characteristics of hackathons, such as their competitive nature, the intensity of team collaboration, and the objective of generating innovative solutions within a concentrated timeframe. Halvari et al. (2020) suggest that a hackathon, as a concept, encompasses nine necessary and sufficient attributes that define it: organization, limited duration, collocation, challenge, ceremonial process, team, objective, collaboration, and creation process.

Originating from the software development industry, where they were established as competitive events for creative problem-solving and new prototype development, hackathons have expanded into broader domains, including social project initiation and ideation for addressing social issues. Hackathons can also be conceptualized as friendly activities or competitions used by software programmers and other domain experts to develop solutions for a specific challenge over a short and predetermined period (Mehta and Shah, 2022).

Corporate Venture Capital

Corporate Venture Capital (CVC) involves direct investments in innovative startups by corporations seeking to access emerging technologies and new business models. Pinkow and Iversen (2020) argue that corporate venture capital represents a crucial strategy in the realm of open innovation, providing organizations with a structured method to access external

innovations and respond to the rapidly evolving dynamics of markets and technologies. An important aspect mentioned by Kortum and Lerner (2002) states that CVC cannot be separated from the traditional concept of venture capital, as both forms of financing are interdependent. The authors define the three essential characteristics of CVC as providing investment capital to young and rapidly growing companies, offering management support, and maintaining a long-term perspective.

Building on this foundation, Pinkow and Iversen (2020) categorize the strategic objectives of CVC into three main areas: strengthening the core business, leveraging the ecosystem, and exploring new markets and technologies. Strengthening the core business through CVC involves investing in startups or entrepreneurial ventures that can enhance the corporation's current position and core competencies. This approach allows corporations to improve internal research and development efficiency and protect their existing business by identifying disruptive technologies that could pose potential threats. Leveraging the ecosystem focuses on creating and enhancing a robust ecosystem around the core business by investing in companies operating in complementary markets. The goal is to stimulate demand for the corporation's existing products and technologies and facilitate the transfer of knowledge and skills, thereby contributing to sustainable innovation and creating new growth opportunities. Exploring new markets and technologies through a CVC strategy aims at identifying and adopting emerging innovations that lie outside the corporation's primary field of activity. This approach provides the opportunity to access new technical and market knowledge, supporting technological diversification and expanding the corporation's portfolio in new and innovative directions.

Open Source

Open source refers to the practice of making software source code freely available for anyone to use, modify, and distribute. This strategy encourages collaborative development and knowledge sharing, leading to faster innovation and broader adoption of technologies. Open-source development is fundamental to creating shared technological resources, facilitating an environment of collective progress and innovation.

Among other criteria, a fundamental requirement for open-source projects is the availability of the source code, as its absence would make the development or evolution of the software extremely difficult, if not impossible (Gacek and Arief, 2004).

West and Gallagher (2005) state that viewing open source as an open innovation strategy encompasses two key elements: shared rights to use the technology and the collaborative development of that technology. However, they note that unlike individual participants, firms must also consider capturing economic returns to justify their investment. West and Gallagher (2005) identified four approaches to open innovation in the context of open-source software.

- *Pooled R&D* represent a model that involves firms collaborating to contribute to shared research and development efforts. A well-known example is the support for the Linux operating system through the Open Source Development Lab.
- *Spinouts* are an approach that involve transforming internal development projects into externally visible open-source projects.
- *Selling complements* is a method focused on selling goods and services that complement a core innovation.
- *Donation of complements*, a scenario in which firms generate revenue from the core innovation but seek to donate certain complements. An example is the mods for computer games, where game publishers release editing tools to encourage users to create customized versions of the games, therefore extending the product's lifecycle and maintaining the consumer interest.

Synergies among Open Innovation Strategies

It is important to note that these open innovation strategies, co-creation, crowdsourcing, intellectual property and licensing, hackathons, and open source do not operate in isolation but often overlap and interconnect. For instance, crowdsourcing can significantly enrich the co-creation process by bringing in diverse perspectives and ideas from a wide pool of participants. A prime example is the LEGO Ideas platform, where fans submit their own designs, which are then reviewed and potentially produced by LEGO, merging crowdsourcing with co-creation.

Similarly, sharing intellectual property can lead to new collaborations within co-creation initiatives, fostering a more dynamic and innovative environment. For example, pharmaceutical companies often license their technologies to universities and research institutions, which then collaborate to develop new drugs, combining the strengths of both parties.

Hackathons often incorporate elements of co-creation and crowdsourcing, creating intense, collaborative efforts that drive rapid innovation. Events like the NASA Space Apps Challenge bring together coders, scientists, designers and space enthusiasts to solve complex problems using open data provided by NASA, blending hackathons with crowdsourcing and co-creation.

Additionally, open-source projects grow on the principles of co-creation and crowdsourcing, enabling continuous development and improvement through shared knowledge and resources. The Linux operating system is an emblematic example, where developers from around the world contribute to the codebase, enhancing and expanding its capabilities through a collaborative, open-source model.

This integrated approach enhances the effectiveness of each strategy, leading to more impactful and sustainable innovation outcomes, summarized in Table 1. By utilizing these interconnected strategies, organizations can build a robust innovation ecosystem that taps into the collective intelligence and creativity of a diverse range of contributors.

Table 1. Open Innovation Strategies in relation to the co-creation process

<i>Open Innovation Strategies</i>	<i>Co-Creation process</i>
<i>Crowdsourcing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrich the process by adding new perspectives and ideas • Developed platforms
<i>Intellectual property</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance new collaboration • Fostering dynamic and innovative environment
<i>Hackathons</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generates rapid innovation • Use crowdsourcing as collaborative effort
<i>Open source</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unrestricted way of co-creation • Enables continuous development and improvement • Allows knowledge and resources sharing

Conclusion

Open innovation strategies, encompassing co-creation, crowdsourcing, intellectual property sharing, hackathons, and open-source development, are vital for modern enterprises seeking a competitive edge. These strategies facilitate the integration of external ideas and technologies, promoting a dynamic and adaptive innovation process.

This study demonstrates that these strategies are not isolated but interlinked, creating a synergetic effect that amplifies their individual benefits. While the reliance on secondary data and case studies provides valuable insights, further empirical research is needed to explore the practical challenges and broader applicability across different industries. Adopting a holistic approach to open innovation, enterprises can then build an innovative ecosystem, positioning themselves for sustainable growth and success in a rapidly changing market environment.

In conclusion, the successful implementation of open innovation strategies requires a strategic and well-coordinated effort across the organization. Firms must foster an environment that values collaboration, transparency, and knowledge sharing. By doing so, they can harness the full potential of open innovation, leading to sustained competitive advantage and long-term success. Future research should focus on developing frameworks and tools to support the practical application of these strategies, ensuring that businesses can effectively navigate the complexities of open innovation and fully realize its benefits.

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